

Assessing Economic Reforms in Nigeria in the Light of Bentham's Principle of Utility

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Abstract

This paper examines Nigeria's recent economic reforms using Jeremy Bentham's principle of utility, which posits that policies should be evaluated based on their ability to maximize the greatest good for the greatest number of people. The study focused on key economic initiatives implemented by President Bola Tinubu's administration, including the controversial removal of fuel subsidies and the unification of exchange rates. With Bentham's utilitarian framework, the research analyzes the potential long-term benefits of these reforms against their immediate societal impacts, particularly on vulnerable populations. The paper used philosophical analysis to assess whether these economic reforms are embedded in utilitarian principle of greatest good to the greatest number and found them wanting in that regard. The paper concluded by suggesting ways to enhance the integration of utilitarian principles in Nigerian economic policymaking, including the development of more sophisticated social impact assessment tools and greater emphasis on public consultation through the use of long term profitable policies. It proposed that the purpose of policy making should be to satisfy the useful needs and not just for the sake of policy making. Economic reforms should demonstrate usefulness to the economy and the people and not just theories that have no usefulness to the citizens and the economy.

Keywords: *Economy, Nigeria, Reform, utility and utilitarianism.*

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Introduction

Economic reform is a set of changes to a country's economic system aimed at improving its efficiency, stability, and growth. Economic reforms may entail deregulation, privatisation, tax reforms and withdrawal of social benefits. If properly planned and implemented, economic reforms engender health market competition, consolidation of financial institutions, improved market economy's infrastructure and invariably raise the people's standard of living.

Economic reform can also include macroeconomic reforms, such as: controlling inflation, reducing public debt, ensuring fiscal and monetary discipline, and eliminating macroeconomic imbalances.

In a nutshell, economic reform is "a radical change process that increases living standards, improves well-being, and increases resistance against shocks in order to provide permanent and long-term improvement and solutions" (Infoscipedia, n.d.).

Nigerian government has embarked on so many economic reforms most of which, regrettably, yielded no positive dividends. It is lamentable that most of these economic reforms brought untold hardship on the people who are often persuaded to bear the anomaly for future positive ends. Unfortunately the hope

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of future positive ends has become tantalizing as the excruciating pains of the reforms increase with change of administration.

Given the situation in Nigeria and the growing hardship among Nigerians, there is a need to question and understand how effectively Nigeria's economic reforms have conformed to Bentham's principle of utility, maximising the greatest good for the greatest number of citizens. This question lies at the heart of assessing the success and ethical implications of Nigeria's economic policies over the past decades. As Africa's largest economy and most populous nation, Nigeria's economic development has significant implications not only for its citizens but for the entire continent. The country's vast oil reserves and potential for agricultural and industrial development make it a key player in the region, but persistent challenges in translating these resources into widespread prosperity underscore the need for a critical examination of its economic reform strategies.

Economic reform has been a key focus across Africa as nations strive to overcome colonial legacies, political instability and systemic corruption. In Nigeria, successive governments have implemented various economic policies aimed at stimulating growth, reducing poverty and improving general welfare. However, the continent's history is replete with examples of well-intentioned reforms that have failed to deliver on their promises, often exacerbating inequality and social tensions (Ake, 1996). The Nigerian experience mirrors that of many African countries where structural adjustment programmes, privatisation initiatives and efforts to attract foreign investment have produced mixed results, raising questions about the appropriateness of imported economic models in the African context.

Scholars have approached the evaluation of economic reforms through various lenses, including neoclassical economics, dependency theory and institutional economics. While these perspectives offer valuable insights, they often fall short of providing a comprehensive ethical framework for assessing the human impact of economic policies. For example, Rodrik argues that successful economic reforms must be context-specific and tailored to local institutional capabilities, challenging the one-size-fits-all approach often advocated by international financial institutions (Rodrik, 2006), while Acemoglu and Robinson highlight the crucial role of inclusive institutions in promoting sustainable economic growth, suggesting that reforms that fail to address underlying power structures are unlikely to succeed (Acemoglu, & Robinson, 2012). Despite these important contributions, there remains a gap in the evaluation of economic policies from an explicitly ethical perspective that considers the overall welfare of the population.

Jeremy Bentham's utilitarian philosophy, centered on the principle of utility, posits that the moral value of an action (or in this case a policy) should be judged by its consequences and its ability to promote the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people (Bentham, 2007). This principle provides a compelling ethical lens through which to examine the efficacy and morality of economic reforms, especially in a diverse and complex nation like Nigeria. Utilitarianism provides a framework for balancing competing interests and assessing the distribution of benefits and burdens across society, which is particularly relevant in a country characterised by significant ethnic, religious and economic diversity.

This paper applies Bentham's utilitarian framework to assess key economic reforms in Nigeria, focusing on policies implemented under the administration of President Bola Tinubu. Key initiatives to be examined include the removal of fuel subsidies to redirect funds towards critical infrastructure and social services, and ongoing efforts to tackle systemic corruption and improve fiscal responsibility. We will assess the impact of these reforms on overall social welfare, paying particular attention to their impact on different segments of Nigerian society, including the urban poor, rural communities and the emerging middle class. We will also critically analyse the shortcomings of these reforms, such as the persistently high levels of poverty and unemployment, in the light of utilitarian principles.

The analysis will also consider the unique challenges Nigeria faces in implementing economic reforms, including the 'resource curse' associated with oil dependence, widespread corruption and regional disparities. We will examine how these factors have influenced the design and implementation of economic policies, and assess whether the utilitarian goal of maximising overall societal welfare has been

adequately prioritised. In addition, the paper will explore the tension between short-term economic gains and long-term sustainable development, and consider how this balance can be reconciled with Bentham's principle of utility.

By applying a utilitarian framework to the evaluation of economic reforms, this study seeks to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of policy effectiveness that goes beyond traditional economic indicators to consider the broader impact on human welfare and social justice.

An Insight on some Economic Reforms in Tinubu's Government

President Bola Tinubu's ascension to power in Nigeria in 2023 marks a pivotal moment in the country's economic trajectory. As Africa's largest economy and most populous nation, Nigeria has long grappled with the challenge of translating its vast natural resources and human capital into sustainable economic growth and improved living standards for its citizens. Economic reform has been a recurring theme in Nigerian governance, with each administration attempting to address persistent problems such as poverty, unemployment, inflation and overdependence on oil revenues. Coming at a time of global economic uncertainty and domestic fiscal pressures, the Tinubu administration has been tasked with implementing transformative economic policies aimed at stabilising the economy and laying the foundations for long-term prosperity (Nwokoye, & Adegboye, 2022).

Tinubu inherited an economy beset by multiple challenges. Years of fiscal mismanagement, coupled with the global economic shocks of the COVID-19 pandemic and fluctuating oil prices, had left Nigeria in a precarious economic situation (World Bank, 2023). The country faced high rates of inflation, a widening budget deficit, a complex multiple exchange rate system and unsustainable subsidy regimes that drained public resources (International Monetary Fund, 2023). The Tinubu administration adopted an economic philosophy centred on fiscal responsibility, market-oriented reforms and economic diversification. Key objectives included stabilising the macro-economy, attracting foreign investment, boosting domestic productivity and improving the overall business environment. However, these ambitious goals faced significant challenges, including entrenched interests resistant to change, infrastructure deficits, security concerns, and the immediate social impact of reforms on an already struggling population (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023).

In response to these challenges, Tinubu's government introduced several key economic reforms. One of the most significant and controversial was the removal of the long-standing fuel subsidy (Aina, & Onwuka, 2023). This policy, aimed at freeing up fiscal resources for investment in critical sectors, was implemented despite concerns about its immediate inflationary impact on citizens (Vanguard News, 2023). The fuel subsidy, which had been in place for decades, was widely regarded as unsustainable, costing the government billions of dollars annually and distorting market dynamics. However, it had also become a form of social welfare that many Nigerians relied on to cope with economic hardship.

The removal of the subsidy was abrupt, announced during Tinubu's inauguration speech, and took many by surprise (Adebayo, 2023). The immediate effect was a sharp increase in fuel prices, which rippled through the economy, affecting transport costs, food prices and overall inflation. The government argued that the savings from subsidy removal would be channeled into infrastructure development, healthcare, education and other critical sectors that could drive long-term economic growth and improve living standards (Reuters, 2023). To mitigate the short-term impact, the administration proposed a series of palliative measures, including wage increases for public sector workers and plans for a more robust social safety net (Nigeria Presidency, 2023). However, the implementation of these measures faced logistical challenges and scepticism from a public wary of previous unfulfilled government promises.

Another major initiative was the unification of the exchange rate, moving away from the previous multiple rate system to a more market-determined rate. This policy was designed to increase transparency, reduce arbitrage opportunities and boost investor confidence in the Nigerian economy (Premium Times, 2023). The multiple exchange rate system, which had been in place for several years, was widely criticised

for creating distortions in the economy, encouraging corruption and deterring foreign investment (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023).

Under the new policy, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) allowed the naira to float more freely, effectively devaluing the currency against major international currencies such as the US dollar (International Monetary Fund, 2023). The move was aimed at narrowing the gap between the official exchange rate and the parallel market rate, which had widened considerably and led to speculation and a thriving black market in foreign exchange. The unification of the exchange rate was expected to have several positive effects on the Nigerian economy. First, it was expected to improve the allocation of foreign exchange resources, ensuring that scarce foreign exchange was directed to productive economic activities rather than speculative transactions (Financial Times, 2023). Secondly, the policy was expected to enhance the competitiveness of Nigerian exports by allowing the currency to find its true value, potentially boosting non-oil exports and supporting the government's economic diversification agenda (Nigerian Economic Summit Group, 2023).

However, the immediate impact of the policy was a significant depreciation of the naira, which raised concerns about imported inflation given Nigeria's heavy reliance on imported goods (Export Promotion Council, 2023). This depreciation added to the inflationary pressures already present from the removal of fuel subsidies, creating a challenging economic environment for businesses and consumers alike. The government and the CBN emphasized that the short-term pains of the policy would be outweighed by long-term gains, including increased foreign direct investment, improved foreign exchange liquidity, and a more robust and transparent foreign exchange market (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023). They also implemented measures to support key sectors of the economy during the transition period, including preferential access to foreign exchange for manufacturers importing essential raw materials (Ministry of Finance, 2023).

In addition, the administration embarked on tax reforms that focused on broadening the tax base and improving collection efficiency rather than increasing tax rates. These reforms included efforts to digitise tax administration and close loopholes in the system (Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2023). The government also initiated policies to support agricultural productivity and food security, recognising the sector's potential for job creation and economic diversification (Federal Inland Revenue Service, 2023). In addition, the Tinubu administration announced plans for large-scale infrastructure development, particularly in the transport and energy sectors, to address long-standing bottlenecks in the economy (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2023). Each of these policies was presented as part of a coherent strategy to reposition Nigeria's economy for sustainable growth, although their implementation and immediate impact have been the subject of intense national debate (Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission, 2023).

Ewang, in an article titled "Hope or Hardship for Nigeria? Tinubu's Economic Reforms and their Fallout", laments that the economic reforms of Tinubu in Nigeria dashed his campaign mantra of renewed hope. She avers that people started with Tinubu's inaugural speech that "announced the abrupt removal of fuel consumption subsidy without adequate compensatory measures" (Premium Times, 2023). The repercussion of that claimed to be measure to fast-track economic recovery resulted to vicious circle of economic woes that "have contributed to Nigeria's worst cost of living crisis in almost 30 years, pushing millions of people deeper into poverty" (Ewang, 2024).

In her opinion,

The president, who inherited an ailing economy, also liberalized the exchange rate, leading to a sharp depreciation of the Naira that also contributed to the high inflation. He justified these changes as "painful yet necessary" to correct decades of economic mismanagement, pointing out that the fuel subsidy system was among other things rife with corruption that was contributing to draining government finances (Ewang, 2024).

However, the intended dividend is still far from being achieved as devaluation of currency compounded the situation. Even measures purportedly put in place to cushion the effects of the harsh economic policies failed woefully as

Nigeria lacks a comprehensive rights-aligned social security system that provides income support for people throughout their lives. While ad hoc programs are at times introduced to address specific crises – such as the economic hardships caused by the Covid-19 pandemic and the present inflation – these initiatives are often insufficient, temporary and reach only a tiny fraction of people (Ewang, 2024).

She suggests that for any economic policy in Nigeria to achieve its result, “government should design rights-driven and people-centered policies, ensuring that human rights guide the formulation and implementation of significant policy changes like removing subsidies. It is also important for the government to prioritize transparency and public engagement” (Ewang, 2024). It is lack of these requirements that deprived Tinubu’s economic policies of utilitarian principle which every economic reform directed at the good of the people must imbibe.

Also reacting to economic reforms in Nigeria, Esekpa, Ekarika & Njama agree that fuel subsidy precipitates a lot of challenges including corruption, issues of smuggling, unsustainable financial cost of subsidy and investment challenges which stunt economic growth (Ewang, 2024). They believe that: “Even when the rational principals are graduated on income distribution, employment and security risk. However, this is more favourable to rich more than the poor”. For them, the economic impact of fuel subsidy removal can be group into long and short term.

The short-term impact to the rich includes government deficit, economic resource needed investment, security risk and incentive to trillions of naira while the long-term impact is associated with leverage on African continental free credit rating (AFCFTA), improvement in sovereign product availability. This further includes the de-regulation of down-stream sector, and proper encouragement of local refineries, creation of employment opportunity, increased in revenue proceeds availability of economic product, reduction in borrowing, market competition, generation of foreign exchange and economic growth (Esekpa, Ekarika, & Njama, 2024).

They take a stand that “issue of fuel subsidy is unsustainable and may lead to impediment to debt crisis, poverty and inflation” (Esekpa, Ekarika, & Njama, 2024). It “is seen as feasible disruption that follows such a decision that affect the economy mostly than that of the projected benefit from fuel subsidy removal monthly in short- and long-term processes” (Esekpa, Ekarika, & Njama, 2024). They, therefore, recommend that government should increase revenue among works force as a way of elimination transport problem; encourage individual to establish refineries to boost the local capacity of production of petroleum product; provide cheaper alternative means of transportation as way of reducing hardship and inflation; and give education and healthcare greater attention (Esekpa, Ekarika, & Njama, 2024).

An Overview on Jeremy Bentham Utility Theory

Jeremy Bentham, an English philosopher and social reformer, introduced utilitarianism in the late 18th century, marking a significant shift in moral philosophy. Born in 1748, Bentham developed his ideas at a time of profound social and economic change, as the Industrial Revolution began to transform British society. His utilitarian philosophy was a radical departure from the prevailing moral theories of his time, which were largely based on religious doctrine or abstract notions of natural rights. Bentham's approach was revolutionary in its emphasis on empirical observation and quantifiable outcomes rather than a priori moral principles. He proposed that the morality of an action should be judged solely by its consequences, specifically its ability to promote happiness or reduce suffering. This consequentialist approach challenged the deontological ethics that dominated eighteenth-century thought and offered a more pragmatic and potentially egalitarian basis for moral and political decision-making (Esekpa, Ekarika, & Njama, 2024).

At the heart of Bentham's theory of utility is the principle of utility, often summarised as 'the greatest good for the greatest number'. This principle states that the moral value of an action is determined solely by its contribution to general happiness or well-being. Bentham defined utility in hedonistic terms, equating it with the presence of pleasure and the absence of pain. He argued that these sensations were the ultimate arbiters of value in human experience. Crucially, Bentham's theory was egalitarian in its insistence that each individual's pleasure and pain should be given equal weight in moral calculations. This democratic aspect of utilitarianism was radical for its time, implying that the welfare of the common man was as morally significant as that of the elite. Bentham extended this principle to all sentient beings, arguing that the capacity to suffer was the key consideration in moral deliberations, rather than rationality or other human-specific characteristics (Crimmins, 2019).

To operationalise his theory, Bentham proposed the felicific calculus (also known as the hedonistic calculus), a systematic method for quantifying and comparing different pleasures and pains. This calculus aimed to provide a rational basis for moral and political decision-making by reducing complex social issues to a set of quantifiable variables. Bentham identified seven key dimensions of pleasure and pain: intensity, duration, certainty, propinquity (proximity in time), fecundity (likelihood of producing similar sensations), purity (likelihood of not being followed by opposite sensations) and extent (number of people affected). By assessing actions or policies along these dimensions, Bentham believed it would be possible to calculate their overall utility and thus determine the most ethical course of action. However, the practical implementation of the felicific calculus faced significant challenges, including the difficulty of accurately measuring subjective experience and the complexity of aggregating diverse individual utilities into a meaningful societal measure (Driver, 2014).

Bentham's theory of utility is particularly relevant to economic policy-making, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. It provides a framework for evaluating policies based on their overall impact on societal welfare, rather than narrow economic indicators. In the Nigerian context, this approach could inform resource allocation decisions by weighing short-term costs against long-term benefits. For example, evaluating policies such as subsidy removal or infrastructure investment through a utilitarian lens would require careful consideration of their impact across different socio-economic groups and over time. However, applying utilitarian principles to real economic problems in Nigeria faces several challenges. These include the difficulty of accurately measuring and comparing benefits across a diverse population, the risk of overlooking minority interests in pursuit of majority benefits, and the challenge of balancing immediate economic hardship against potential future gains. Despite these difficulties, the utilitarian approach offers valuable insights for Nigerian policymakers and encourages a more holistic view of economic development that considers social welfare alongside traditional economic measures (Schofield, 2006).

Implications of Bentham's Utility theory on Economic reforms in Nigeria

Utilitarianism, as conceptualised by Jeremy Bentham, provides a background for economic policy making, especially in the context of developing economies like Nigeria. The principle of maximising "the greatest good for the greatest number" provides a clear ethical guideline for policy formulation and evaluation. In economic terms, this translates into the maximisation of social welfare, a concept formalized in modern economics through social welfare functions (Okoye, 2020). These functions attempt to aggregate individual utilities into a measure of societal well-being, closely following Bentham's vision of a hedonistic calculus. Utilitarian principles can inform the cost-benefit analysis of economic policies by encouraging policymakers to consider the broad societal implications of their decisions, rather than focusing solely on narrow economic indicators. This approach is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where economic reforms often have far-reaching consequences for different socio-economic groups.

Applying Bentham's theory of utility to specific Nigerian economic reforms provides interesting insights. Consider the recent fuel subsidy removal policy implemented by the Tinubu's administration in 2023. From a utilitarian perspective, this reform can be analysed in terms of its potential to maximise overall

societal welfare. While the immediate impact of increased fuel prices negatively affects a large portion of the population, the long-term benefits of redirecting subsidy funds to infrastructure, health and education could potentially yield greater utility for a larger number of citizens (Adebayo, 2023). Similarly, the policy of exchange rate unification can be evaluated through a utilitarian lens. The short-term pain of currency depreciation could be outweighed by the long-term benefits of increased foreign investment, improved export competitiveness and a more transparent foreign exchange market, potentially leading to broader economic growth and job creation (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). However, these assessments must carefully weigh short-term hardships against projected long-term gains, a challenging task in the Nigerian context.

The implementation of utilitarian principles in Nigeria's economic policymaking faces significant challenges. The country's complex socio-economic landscape, characterised by high levels of wealth inequality, ethnic diversity and regional disparities, complicates the calculation of overall societal utility. For example, policies that maximise utility at the national level may disproportionately benefit certain ethnic groups or regions, potentially exacerbating existing tensions (Osaghae, 2021). Furthermore, Nigeria's political constraints, including entrenched interests and short-term electoral considerations, often prevent the implementation of policies that may maximise long-term societal welfare but impose short-term costs on influential groups. The lack of robust data collection and analysis systems also makes it difficult to accurately assess the impact of policies on different segments of society.

The application of strict utilitarian principles to economic policy in Nigeria also raises significant ethical considerations. Critics argue that a purely utilitarian approach can justify policies that severely disadvantage minority groups or the most vulnerable members of society in the name of maximising overall welfare (Okoye, 2020). In the context of a developing economy like Nigeria, where a significant proportion of the population lives in poverty, there's a risk that utilitarian calculations may undervalue the acute suffering of the poorest in favour of aggregate economic gains. Furthermore, the difficulty of quantifying and comparing different types of utility (e.g. economic growth versus social stability) poses a philosophical challenge to the practical application of Bentham's theory in complex policy decisions.

Despite these challenges, Bentham's theory of utility holds considerable potential for improving future economic reforms in Nigeria. Policymakers could incorporate utilitarian principles more systematically by developing comprehensive social impact assessment tools that attempt to quantify the effects of policies on different social groups and over different time horizons. This could involve the creation of more sophisticated social welfare functions that take into account factors such as income distribution, access to education and health care, and environmental sustainability. In addition, greater emphasis on public consultation and participatory policy-making could help to ensure that different perspectives are taken into account in benefit calculations. Transparency in policy formulation and implementation, coupled with robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, could also enhance the application of utilitarian principles in Nigeria's economic reforms.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the application of Bentham's theory of utility to Nigeria's economic reforms offers valuable insights, but also reveals significant complexities. The theory provides a useful ethical framework for evaluating policies based on their potential to maximise overall societal welfare. However, its practical implementation in Nigeria's diverse and challenging socio-economic context presents significant difficulties. Analysing specific reforms, such as fuel subsidy removal and exchange rate unification, through a utilitarian lens highlights the tension between short-term costs and long-term benefits, as well as the challenges of accurately assessing and aggregating societal benefits. The ethical considerations raised, particularly regarding the potential for utilitarian approaches to justify policies that may disadvantage vulnerable groups, underscore the need for a suitable application of the theory. Going forward, the integration of utilitarian principles into Nigerian economic policymaking could be improved through more sophisticated impact assessment tools, greater public participation and improved healthy

living amongst citizens. Determining the criteria for utility for everybody is still debatable and serious as a philosophical issue.

References

- Acemoglu, D., & Robinson, J. A. (2012). *Why nations fail: The origins of power, prosperity, and poverty*. Profile Books Ltd.
- Adebayo, J. (2023). Impact of subsidy removal on the Nigerian economy. *Daily Trust*, 10-11.
- Aina, O., & Onwuka, D. (2023). Fiscal reforms and economic stabilization in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Economics and Financial Studies*, 15(2), 101–118.
- Ake, C. (1996). *Democracy and development in Africa*. Brookings Institution Press.
- Bentham, J. (2007). *An introduction to the principles of morals and legislation*. Dover Publications.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2023). *Annual Economic Report*.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2023). *Monetary Policy Committee Communique No. 144*. Retrieved August 15, 2024, from <https://www.cbn.gov.ng>
- Crimmins, J. E. (2019). Jeremy Bentham. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2019 Edition). Retrieved on September 17, 2024, from <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2019/entries/bentham/>
- Driver, J. (2014). The history of utilitarianism. In E. N. Zalta (Ed.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2014 Edition), p. 117.
- Esekpa, O. I., Ekarika, W. A., & Njama, G. J. (2024). Economic implications of fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Public Administration, Policy and Governance Research*, 2(3), 202-205.
- Ewang, A. (2024, October 24). Hope or hardship for Nigeria? Tinubu's economic reforms and their fallout. *BTI Blog (Bertelsmann Foundation)*. Retrieved on January 15, 2025, from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2024/10/24/hope-or-hardship-nigeria-tinubus-economic-reforms-and-their-fallout>
- Export Promotion Council. (2023). *Potential impact of exchange rate unification on non-oil exports*.
- Federal Inland Revenue Service. (2023). *Tax Reforms and Digitalization*.
- Financial Times. (2023). Nigeria moves to unify exchange rates in bid to boost economy.
- Infoscipedia. (n.d.). *What is economic reforms*. Retrieved January 19, 2025, from <https://www.igi-global.com/dictionary/second-generation-reforms/9057>
- Infrastructure Concession Regulatory Commission. (2023). *Infrastructure Development in Nigeria: Policy and Practice*.
- International Monetary Fund. (2023). *Nigeria: Article IV consultation—Press release; staff report; and statement by the executive director for Nigeria*.
- International Monetary Fund. (2023). *Nigeria: Article IV consultation—Press release*.
- Manufacturers Association of Nigeria. (2023). *MAN's Position on Forex Policy and Manufacturing Sector*. MAN Press Release.
- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. (2023). *Policies to Support Agricultural Productivity and Food Security in Nigeria*. Retrieved on September 16, 2024, from <https://www.minagri.ng>
- Ministry of Finance. (2023). *Economic outlook following exchange rate reforms*. Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning.

- National Bureau of Statistics. (2023). *Consumer Price Index June 2023*. NBS Report.
- Nigeria Presidency. (2023). *Economic reforms and palliative measures*.
- Nigerian Economic Summit Group. (2023). *Policy brief on exchange rate unification*.
- Nwokoye, O., & Adegboye, O. (2022). Nigeria's economic trajectory: Past policies and future directions. *African Journal of Economic Policy*, 23(1), 34–56.
- Okoye, A. (2020). Ethical implications of economic policies in developing countries: A case study of Nigeria. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 165(2), 215-229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-019-04107-2>
- Osaghae, E. E. (2021). Ethnic politics and governance in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Ethnopolitics*, 20(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17449057.2020.1776255>
- Premium Times. (2023). Debates on Nigeria's economic reforms under Tinubu. *Premium Times*, p. 17.
- Reuters. (2023). Nigeria's Tinubu ends fuel subsidy, sparking price surge. *Reuters Africa*.
- Rodrik, D. (2006). Goodbye Washington Consensus, hello Washington confusion? A review of the World Bank's Economic Growth in the 1990s: Learning from a Decade of Reform. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 44(4), 973–987. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jel.44.4.973>
- Schofield, P. (2006). *Utility and democracy: The political thought of Jeremy Bentham*. Oxford University Press.
- Vanguard News. (2023). Economic implications of Tinubu's subsidy removal policy, 5–7
- World Bank. (2023). *Nigeria economic update: Navigating the headwinds*.

